

Monsters, Mythical Creatures, and Island Hopping in Seychellois Folktales

Thérésia Penda Choppy

Introduction

Seychelles' folklore is populated by various mythical creatures that reflect the polyglot linguistic reality of Seychellois society. Bearing in mind that Seychelles is a creolized, island society which has been fashioned out of European colonialism and slavery during the 18th and 19th centuries, combined with the precolonial Indian Ocean World phenomenon, this polyglot linguistic reality is not surprising. Being one of the most important tools of diasporic memories, the folktale genre is naturally a palimpsest of the cultural interchanges which have taken place throughout the region's history, including the precolonial Indian Ocean World. For example, Haring points out that even before East African stories were transported to the plantation islands via slavery, they were enriched by interchanges between Austronesians and Bantus in Madagascar (2003: 20). Stories from the Swahili Civilization had also been enriched by interchanges with the Arab Civilization (Geider, 2004). This interchange in the folktale genre included not only the content, that is, tale types and motifs, but also structural devices such as framing one story into another.

The most obvious results of these cultural interchanges are the mythical creatures and monsters that populate Seychellois stories – creatures that sometimes have names in unknown languages, or meanings that we think we know, but are really the consequences of sense-making in a linguistic environment where origins and meanings are blurred. In the context of the Indian Ocean World, all of these mythical characters have entered the Seychellois folktale tradition through island hopping. Some of the characters have taken root and expanded, whilst others have remained obscure. This paper will begin by giving an overview of how these creatures travelled from one set of islands to another within the Indian Ocean basin, and proceed to discuss each one as an individual case study.

Contextually, it is worth mentioning that this present study is one of the findings of a larger study which attempts to trace the origins of the stories in the Seychellois folktale repertoire. As such, a database of about 200 folktales was compiled and classified in a dataset as per the Arne, Thompson and Uther (ATU) folktale classification system (2014). For example, '*Sandriyonn*' and '*Makaya*' have both been classified as 510A because they are both versions of 'Cinderella', which is the prototype of 510A in the ATU system. Using a mixed methods approach, the data has been analysed quantitatively, in terms of their importance and impact,

and qualitatively in terms of what their content signifies. The tools employed were Google Sheets and Nvivo. For this study in particular, content analysis and comparative analysis have been especially useful. The review of literature has also played a pivotal role in making important links between different traditions and symbols, and various collections compiled in different historical periods.

Part 1: Island Hopping

In its folktale repertoire, Seychelles is deeply connected to other Southwest Indian Ocean islands, in that it shares the same mythical creatures and monsters as these islands, as well as other characteristics of folklore. Lee Haring speaks of a ‘common stock of stories’ with regards to this region, which is due to several layers of migration under different historical circumstances (2003: 20). Haring’s book, ‘Stars and Keys: Folktales and Creolization in the Indian Ocean’ (2007), actually illustrates this common stock, by giving examples of the same stories or folktale characters in each of these islands. The most remarkable of these include a character which Haring calls ‘The Defiant Girl’; the Malagasy malevolent spirit, *lolo*; the Bantu swallowing monster; and varieties of European propagated stories such as ‘Cinderella’ and ‘The Devil and the Smith’. Even though Seychelles is commonly thought to have been uninhabited prior to colonization in the late 17th century (Scarr, 2000; Franda, 1982), the story of its rich folklore starts well before colonization, during the maritime migrations of islanders from Borneo or the Sulawesi islands between the 6th and 9th centuries, to East Africa and Madagascar, where they mixed with the Bantus, and consequently creating a new cultural heritage that is particular to the Southwest Indian Ocean (Haring, 2003: 19). Many Bantu tribes also share similar folktale characters and plots, indicating cultural interchange (Haring, 2005: 292). Some Bantu cultures are also creolized societies, for example, the Swahilis, who represent mixtures of African and Arab genetic and cultural features (Horton and Middleton, 2010). There is evidence to suggest that elements of ‘The Arabian Nights’ may have been transferred to the Swahili culture orally, well before Europeans colonized East Africa (Geider, 2007; Mazrui, 2016).

Scholars of the region have named these early cultural transfers and its continuance, ‘The Indian Ocean World’ phenomenon (Ottino, 1974; McPherson, 1984; Schottenhammer, 2019). Its geographical reaches extended from Cape Leeuwin in southwestern Australia to the Cape of Good Hope in Southern Africa (McPherson, 1984: 78). Apart from the early migrations from the Indonesian islands to Eastern Africa, this phenomenon also included coastal areas along the Indian Ocean rim which implicated several important civilizations. These include Eastern and Southern Africa, the horn of Africa, the tail of the Arab peninsula, and Southern India (Blench, 2014). As such, the resulting interactions involved the Bantu, Swahili, Arab, Persian and Indian civilizations, as well as the Malay/Indonesian civilisations.

These interactions and cultural transfers were facilitated by long-distance maritime exchanges (Schottenhammer, 2019). This was consolidated by overland trade and commerce (McPherson, 1984: 80). A good representation of this is a map proposed by Ottino (1974), showing the island and port-hopping routes of these exchanges.

LES ROUTES COMMERCIALES DANS L'OCEAN INDIEN (X^e-XV^e SIECLE)

Figure 1: Commercial routes in the Indian Ocean in the 10th and 15th centuries

(Source: Ottino (1974), p.145)

This map is very significant to the present study of mythical creatures and monsters of Afro-Malagasy origins, which were transferred to Seychelles (and other Southwest Indian Ocean islands) via sea routes. Colonialism and slavery are the points of convergence for the stories that host these creatures. Ancient story repertoires which had already merged on the east coast of Africa and Madagascar, were moved from these areas to the plantation islands of Reunion, Mauritius and Seychelles by French colonists for the purpose of a slave-based exploitation of these islands (Haring, 2005: 291). African and Malagasy slaves had been transported to Mauritius, since 1638 by the Dutch, and later to the Mascarenes (Reunion, then Ile Bourbon, in 1665, then Mauritius or Ile de France, in 1721), a transference which was increased around the 1730s with the expansion of agriculture in these two islands, but also because they became key players in the Indian Ocean slave trade (Nicholls, 2019: 33).

With regards to Seychelles, most of the early French settlers moved with their slaves from Mauritius and Reunion in the last quarter of the 18th century (Franda, 1982; Scarr, 2000; Nicholls, 2019). As such, Seychelles shares the same source of slaves as these two islands. The general areas from which the slaves came include Guinea and the West African coast, the East African coast, from the Cape of Good Hope to the Port of Suez, including Ethiopia and Egypt, and the Malabar Coast from India, and east of the Cape Cormorin area (Sheriff and Teelock, 2016: 27). The slaves who were brought in later, mainly through the illegal slave trade which continued after abolition, and those who were dumped by the British Navy in the 1860s, would have come directly from Madagascar and East Africa (Nicholls, 2019).

Since exiled groups, forced or voluntary, tend to tell the stories from their original homelands as a sort of nostalgic memory making (Haring, 2021),¹ one can use the history of how such islands as the Seychelles were populated to trace the general area from which these stories came. Haring himself has proposed that the bulk of the trickster stories came from East Africa, through comparisons with variants collected among the Makonde, Nyanja, Swahili and other Eastern and Central African peoples which are closest to the types found in Seychelles (2005). As for those concepts in Southwestern Indian Ocean folklore that might have Austronesian links, they are obviously the contributions of the Malagasies whose ancestors made those early migratory trips across the Indian Ocean in the 6th and 9th centuries (Haring, 2003: 19). The *Itrimobe*, which is interlinked with the Bantu swallowing monster, is one such concept (Ottino, 2013: 3).

The spread of Afro-Malagasy mythical folktale characters in the Indian Ocean region through island hopping, was precipitated by (i) European colonial activities in the region, and (ii) the relative proximity of islands and archipelagos which proved very useful for the illicit slave trade that persisted after abolition. Focusing specifically on Seychelles, Peter Nicholls'

¹ Personal communication, November 2021

doctoral thesis makes a very good case for the role of the archipelago in a ‘tightly interwoven commercial nexus’ in the region (2019: 22). Seychelles’ widespread atolls and island groups provided both a way station and ‘smuggling out-station’ for the illicit provisioning of slaves to Reunion and Mauritius, as well as its own smaller plantations on Mahé and the inner islands. In their attempts to fight this illicit trade, the British navy inadvertently also contributed to the consolidation of these folklore characters in the Seychelles intangible heritage by dumping slaves which were still being shipped from the ports and islands of the East African coast, and which had been captured on the high seas. The map below gives an idea of this ‘nexus’.

Figure 2: Map of the Southwest Indian Ocean
 (Source: R.B. Allen (2001), p.92)

Thus, in summary, there were two main eras of island hopping which contributed to the transference of mythical creatures to the folklore of Southwestern Indian Ocean islands, more particularly, Seychelles. The first was through the maritime migrations of Austronesians from the Indonesian islands in the 6th and 9th centuries (Haring, 2003: 19). The second was during the early European colonization of the region, with the first wave of transference in this era moving first from Madagascar and the Comoros to Mauritius (or Reunion), and then to Seychelles once the archipelago was settled (Campbell, 1981; Vernet, 2013; Haring, 2005). The second wave involved mainly slaves from Mozambique and the Swahili coast, which coincided with the inception of free trade in the Mascarenes, thus encouraging more trade amongst merchants of the region (Nicholls, 2019: 54). The last significant transference of folklore through the slave trade occurred in the 1860s, when slavers were intercepted on the high seas by the British, and their cargo dumped into the nearest port, including Seychelles (Choppy and Salomon, 2004). Together with the colonists, these were the tradition bearers who would create the new creolized society and folklore of the Seychelles.

Part 2: The Mythical Creatures

The mythical creatures that inhabit Seychellois stories (and the repertoires of other Southwestern Indian Ocean islands) existed first as the diasporic memories of specific groups, and then as the common heritage of a creolized society. The creolization process often causes metamorphosis in the description and meaning of folktale characters. This occurs when previously diasporic groups who were the vectors of specific elements of folklore, merge with other groups and when the new hybrid generations lose the original languages from which these characters came. Sometimes, original meanings are lost in the process, or new meanings will emerge through evolution, depending on the socio-political conditions of the community. As such, even though most mythical creatures in the Southwestern Indian Ocean repertoires have been inherited from previous, pre-slavery societies, the mythicization process may sometimes also occur in the post-diasporic period through adaptation. For example, whilst the trickster hare is known to be a hare in the Yao and Swahili communities because its name indicates its meaning, in Seychelles it is not recognized as a hare because creolization has phased out these substrate languages and mythicized the character by giving it a new meaning. In this paper, the following mythical creatures from the Seychelles' Afro-Malagasy heritage will be discussed: (i) the trickster, Sounougoula, (ii) the Bantu swallowing monster, (iii) Loulou, (iv) the vanishing woman.

The Trickster Hare, or Sounougoula

In his introduction to his 1983 compilation of Seychellois folktales and riddles, Diallo remarks that one is immediately struck by the frequency of appearance of the Seychellois trickster

hero, Sougoula (p.17). Sougoula is generally known as a mythical personage, whose genetic origin is obscure. He is often described as half man, half animal, with pointed ears and a long tail. Both Choppy and Salomon (2004) and Diallo (1983) concur with this description. Some people conceive Sougoula as being a monkey, probably because of the description of a long tail. This is confirmed by an exercise in 2001, in which several people were asked to draw Sougoula, and most people drew a monkey, with some drawing a man with long pointed ears and a long tail (Choppy and Salomon, 2004: 4).

*Figure 3: Illustration of Sougoula by C. Vincini, Contes de Seychelles
A.Abel (1981)*

Soungoula's main characteristics include duping others, stealing and tricking others to survive and playing pranks on all and sundry, from animals to humans (Diallo, 1983: 17). He is generally seen as a pest by fellow characters in his stories, especially since he almost always manages to escape punishment, again through trickery. The most illustrative example of this is the story of 'Soungoula and the King's Pool' (Choppy and Salomon, 2004: 25-31). This is the story internationally known as 'The Tarbaby and the Rabbit', and classified as ATU 175. In Choppy and Salomon's version, Soungoula, after being caught soiling the king's pool, is confronted by the guards who will take him to face his judgement. He tells them not to tie him up with sisal cords, which make him stronger, whereas banana cords render him helpless. The guards, not sure as to whether he is telling the truth, use banana cords, whereby he escapes. After a chase, Soungoula runs up a banyan tree which has hanging ropes. The guards grab his tail which is still visible, but he sings out that they grabbed the banyan's tail and not his, and when they test it out, he escapes a second time (op. cit. 2004: 30-31). However, Soungoula sometimes meets his match, such as the story of 'Soungoula and the Lion' (ATU 56B) where the lion eats him after he ate the latter's children (Diallo, 1983: 32-36), and the swimming race with the turtle (ATU 275) where he rides on the turtle's back and is drowned when the latter swims underwater (Diallo et al., 1981).

Soungoula is said to have metamorphosed from an earlier trickster known as Konper Lyeve (Hare). According to Norbert Salomon, Konper Lyeve was introduced by the African slaves of the first settlement. Soungoula came in the 1860s with the last waves of slaves who were liberated by the British Navy from Arab and other slave merchants on the high seas, and dumped in Seychelles (Choppy and Salomon, 2004: 1). There are several clues that suggest that this might be true. First, the earliest French settlers of Seychelles came from Mauritius, and some from Reunion (Scarr, 2000; Baker and Corne, 1982; Chaudenson, 1992). The slaves who came with them had already undergone a creolization process and were already creating a new folklore in their new language, Creole, by adapting the stories and characters from their old communities to the new environment (Haring, 2005). Baker and Corne have suggested that there was a significant component of West African slaves in the early creolization period of Mauritius (1982). Since these were likely to have been deliberately mixed up with East African slaves, to avoid recreating new communities from the same areas, it would not be surprising that the name for The Trickster Hare would not be adopted from one of the original African languages, but rather adopted from the dominant French language at the time, thus *Compère Lièvre* or *Compère Lapin* (Chaudenson, 2001: 293-294).

Second, Konper Lyeve seems to have more or less phased out with the first few generations of settlers and their slaves. According to Marcel Rosalie, who was one of the main researchers during the 1980s collection of folklore by the Oral Traditions Unit, the team collected only one story featuring Konper Lyeve instead of Soungoula. This was a version of the race between two animals (ATU 275). However, this story is no longer available in the National Heritage

Research and Protection Documentation Centre (Choppy and Salomon, 2004: 1-2). The fact that this character existed in Seychelles previously is confirmed by the Choppy and Salomon collection (2004) which contains five Konper Lyev stories. It is significant that only two of them are interchangeable with Sounougoula stories, '*Frer Zako i touy son manman*' (The Killing of Mothers – no ATU classification), and '*Konper Lyev kot lanmor Papa Tig,*' (Sham Dead, ATU 50A) which was confirmed by Marcel Rosalie.

The other three stories seem to have more archaic plots and themes, which suggest that they are older than the Sounougoula stories. They portray the hare more as a wise animal than the nasty trickster Sounougoula can be. In '*Konper Lyev i al rod lafors*' (Hare Goes Looking for Strength), Hare goes to the king of the jungle, Lion, to ask for strength so that he can protect himself against the other animals. He is given three tasks which puts him up against bigger, ferocious animals, which he completes with success through his wit. In '*Konper Lyev ek Konper Torti*' (Hare and Tortoise, ATU 225A), the plot resembles more of a creation story, describing how Tortoise's cracks appeared on his shell. Hare teaches him a lesson for sneaking into his work bag to heaven, from where Tortoise falls back to earth. In '*Maryaz Konper Lyev*', (Hare's Wedding, ATU 96), the old Seychellois adage about pregnant wives having impossible wishes is played out, with Hare being sent to look for Loulou's eggs for his pregnant wife, ending with her death from eating the mysteriously acquired eggs. All three stories are typical of the African tradition of using stories to teach moral lessons, all three have descriptions that are closer to the African jungle than the tropical islands of Seychelles. For example, Hare finds the so-called Loulou's eggs underneath a baobab tree, which is very rare in Seychelles, and is said to have been secretly planted by the slaves (Choppy and Salomon, 2004: 51). When Hare goes looking for strength, the animals he is up against are typical African jungle animals – the boa snake, the rhinoceros and the black panther – none of which appear in the Sounougoula stories.

Third, the replacement of Konper Lyev by Sounougoula is part of the linguistic transformation of creolization which is associated with slavery. Sounougoula, which means 'Hare' in Yao and is closely linked to the Swahili *Sungura* (Baker, 1993: 145), is a reinterpretation of the concept of the trickster from its original setting in East Africa where its name indicated the notion of a hare. Because Sounougoula is a sound that in Seychelles Creole had lost its original notional meaning, and was associated only with the notion of a trickster, the word was eventually given a new meaning, and the notion it conveyed was given a new mythological description. Had Konper Lyev been associated with Sounougoula, the latter might not have metamorphosed into the mythical half man, half animal he is known as. Thus, Konper Lyev and Sounougoula are very valuable indicators of cultural and linguistic creolization in Seychelles.

The Swallowing Monster

The swallowing monster is a mythical creature that is associated with the Bantu tradition. This character is found in the stories of Bantu tribes all over Southern Africa (Callaway, 1868; Theal, 1886; Junod, 1897; Jacottet, 1908; Werner, 1933). The original source of this monster is the Congo Basin, and was spread all over Eastern and Southern Africa by the migration of the Bantu peoples (Dseagu, 2021: 3). The core plot is that an oversized monster swallows a whole village and its population, and is eventually killed by a small boy (Werner, 1933: 206). This story is also present in Malagasy myth. In fact, the Malagasy *Itrimobe* is a parallel of the Bantu swallowing monster (Ottino, 2013: 3). The mixing of the Bantu and Malagasy populations has resulted in the fusion of monsters from both traditions. For example, the Indonesian seven-headed snake and the Bantu swallowing monster are sometimes combined (Haring, 2003: 20). In both the Swahili and Malagasy cultures, the swallowing monsters exist in different forms, having in common, an outsized shape that grows as they devour everything in their paths. Some examples include the monstrous cockerel or cat (Chaudenson and Ottino, 1977: 219-251; Beaujard, 1991: 151-204).

Figure 4: Illustration of a Bantu swallowing monster (Usilosimapundu) – a Zulu mythical monster which is associated with landslides and earthquakes.

(Source: A Book of Creatures. Retrieved from: <https://abookofcreatures.com/tag/swallowers/>)

In the Seychellois repertoire, the Afro-Malagasy swallowing monsters range from human beings turned cannibals, to animals and trees that swallow children. ‘*Bononm Bengaye*’, for example, is a story about an old man who eats children in the village. One day, one of his victims kept singing even as he ate her, and gave him instructions to throw all of her bones out of the window. When her mother came to find her, her voice guided her mother in gathering up the bones, shaking them and thus bringing her back to life. The Malagasy heritage is evident in the similarity with the story of Indesoka, the daughter of Itrimobe who was devoured by her father, but brought to life again by her mother, through her bones (Dahle, 1877: 345-351). Many of these stories seem to be designed to warn children against strangers and other dangers in the neighbourhood. Many of these dangers are inherent within humans themselves, in the form of their insatiable desires or their carelessness in breaking taboos. For example, ‘*Bayaya*’ (ATU 315A The Cannibal Sister) is a story about a girl who disobeys her parents and kills a strange bird that her father had caught in the forest. As she prepares it for cooking, the bird sings each step of the preparation, just as in ‘*Bononm Bengaye*’. After consuming the bird, she becomes a devouring monster:

Ene pti moman apré ki ine fini manzé, I vine en gro bebet. La prézan I konmans tay deryer tou poul, kanar, koson é tou zanimu dan lakour. I manzé, manzé meme. Ler ine fini manzé tou bane zanimu I vine pli gro é prézan I poursui son ser.²

As soon as she had eaten it, she became a big monster. Then she started chasing all the chickens, ducks, pigs and all the other animals in the yard. She ate and ate and ate. When she had eaten all the animals, she had become bigger, and she started chasing her sister.

The description of this devouring monster is consistent with both Werner’s (1933) and Ottino’s (2013) descriptions of the swallowing monster. Other similar stories include ‘*Nae dan Pyedibwa Sandegou*’, the story of a little girl who was swallowed by a tree, and ‘*Modita ek Sent Modita*’, a girl whose little sister was swallowed by a snake. However, the most well-known swallowing monster in Seychellois folklore is Loulou, transformed into a devouring pumpkin, in the story named ‘*Tizan, Zann ek Loulou*’. The pumpkin appears towards the end of the story when, after having destroyed Loulou by burning him, the hero, Tizan, wakes up to find a pumpkin vine growing in his ashes. The vine bears a single pumpkin that grows bigger daily, at an amazing rate. Tizan, in spite of being warned to leave the pumpkin alone, cuts its stalk, after which the pumpkin is transformed into a swallowing monster that rolls after him with snapping jaws. The Bantu origin of this story is confirmed by Alice Werner’s ‘*Myths and Legends of the Bantu*’, which includes a devouring pumpkin (1933: 215). Werner refers to a

² National Heritage Research and Protection Section Documentation Centre. Text in original orthography of transcription.

Swahili version of the tale, in which a pumpkin vine springs up in the spot where the ogre died. A pumpkin from the vine breaks off and rolls after some children, trying to swallow them.

This story, Werner says, seems to have originated from the Yao tribe. Yao and Swahili are both Bantu substrate languages of Seychelles Creole. The story, told in Creole, is the result of the creolization process. However, as both Haring (2005) and Ottino (2013) have pointed out, this process had already begun in Madagascar and coastal East Africa where Austronesians and Bantus had mixed, well before the colonial era, which precipitated the spread of the swallowing monster story to Seychelles and the Mascarenes. It is not surprising therefore, that the Seychellois Loulou should represent two types of mythical creatures from two separate cultures – the East African swallowing monster, as represented by the devouring pumpkin, and another type of monster that is more symptomatic of Malagasy lore, known as Loulou. It is for this reason that Loulou is discussed in another context in the next section.

Loulou

Loulou is a character that appears in at least three major folktale categories in the Seychellois repertoire – in stories featuring Tizan, in the trickster stories, and in the larger group classified as ‘Miscellaneous’. Loulou is generally understood by the Seychellois to be a wolf, which is exemplified by Antoine Abel’s comic version of ‘*Tizan, Zann ek Loulou*’, in which Loulou is illustrated as a wolf (1981). Since Loulou has been affirmed to be of Afro-Malagasy origin, one could be excused for being baffled, since wolves have never been associated with either Africa or Madagascar. However, it transpires that Loulou is a transposition of the word ‘*lolo*’ in Malagasy, which means spirit (Haase, 2008: 484). The Malagasy pronunciation, ‘*lul*’ (in IPA), needed only the Creole suffix to become ‘*loulou*’. Time has eroded the original meaning of the word, and it has been reinterpreted as the French word ‘*le loup*’ in stories, which is why some narrators pronounce it *loulou* and some, *lelou*.

Loulou’s Bantu-Malagasy heritage is hardly known in Seychelles. The Malagasy pronunciation and concept of the word ‘*lolo*’ has been lost to time and the reinterpretation that creolization brings. Thus, the Loulou stories are almost always understood at surface level, that is, the character is taken to be an ordinary wolf that wants nothing more than to devour humans and other animals, as it is its natural tendency to do so. The more sinister, supernatural element of the ‘*lolo*’ that is associated with the resurrected dead is somehow lost in translation. That is, until one examines the stories at a deeper level.

The supernatural aspect of Loulou comes out very clearly in the story entitled ‘*Maryaz Konper Lyev*’ (Hare’s Wedding), when the pregnant Mrs. Hare decides that she wants to eat *dizef Loulou*, Loulou’s eggs. After going through great difficulties (being bitten by scorpions, ants,

etc...), Hare is warned by the little gnome-like figure who guards the said Loulou's eggs, that such things have a very high price. This accounts for Hare's very cryptic remark when his wife starts suffering from mysterious stomach pains, after having consumed the eggs: '*Pti Loulou sa!*', meaning, it's the little Loulous! Mrs. Hare of course dies from her mysterious illness. Whereas in certain Loulou stories, one might assume that the wolf is really a wolf and wants nothing more than to devour its prey, it is clear that Mrs. Hare's predator attacks from within, which is very characteristic of Seychellois supernatural beliefs.

Loulou's sinister and malevolent character is deepened in '*Korbo, Sat ek Lisyen*' (a combination of ATU 510A Cinderella, ATU 709 Snow White and ATU 408 The Three Oranges) where again he plays the role of the menacing wolf who eats people. But it is a piece of his claw stuck in a princess's finger that puts her in a deathlike sleep. Thus, in this instance, the wolf has the same effect as the poisoned apple – but once the piece of claw is removed, the princess is rid of the toxic element and regains her health.

In the cosmology and belief systems of the Betsimisaraka and the Tsimihety people in the Maroantsetra region of Northeast Madagascar, Loulou, or Lolo, is one of two spirits which are associated with pure evil, as opposed to Zanahary, which is associated with pure good and equates to the Judeo-Christian 'God' (Golden, 2014: 259). Lolo is also associated with the forest and the water, and is believed to cause quick and violent deaths in a rather capricious manner (Golden, 2014: 260). It is significant that the heroine and the cat find the Loulou family in the forest. In fact, in most of the other Loulou stories in the database, Loulou is associated with the forest.

Even though the narrator of '*Korbo, Sat ek Lisyen*', and a Seychellois audience might understand Loulou as a wolf (which nevertheless represents danger), the sinister quality of its evil has been retained from its original societies before being transferred to Seychelles. This is illustrated by the fact that the evil stepmother's bewitched apple in the creolized version of 'Snow White' has been replaced by Loulou's claw. It causes the same kind of near-death experience which can only be overcome by the removal of the claw. An added dimension of Loulou's evil representation in the story is the narrator's intimation that it stopped trying to get into the princess's house because it was close to day-break and it didn't want to risk any problems along the way. This suggests that Loulou is a thing of the night – something that exists in darkness such as the forest where it resides.

It is interesting to note that the word '*lolo*' in Madagascar was used by the more aristocratic people of a Northern Sakalava kingdom to describe the spirits of Antandroy migrant workers which had risen from the dead, and which ravaged the countryside (Sharp, 2001: 38). The Sakalava and Antandroy people were both included among the Malagasy ethnic groups that were brought to Seychelles as slaves (Benedict and Benedict, 1982: 124-125). The word

'*latandouy*' or '*atandouy*', which is pronounced '*antandouy*' in Malagasy, is used pejoratively in Seychelles Creole, for people of Antandroy descent, and sometimes simply to indicate someone who is considered as no good. Indeed, I have personally witnessed this pejorative use of the word in my community, and native Malagasy speakers have confirmed that the Antandroy are generally marginalized in Madagascar and do the most menial jobs as their tribe is not associated with a specific profession. Could this disdain for the Antandroy and beliefs regarding their transformation as malevolent spirits have been transferred to Seychellois society by Sakalava descendants? And could the Loulou stories have evolved from this? Certainly, it is something that should not be overlooked.

The Vanishing Women

In the Seychelles repertoire, there are at least two stories featuring a character named the Queen of the Sea. The only links that might be made to regional cultures contextually are what is known as the Malagasy water daughter or *Zazavavindrano*. The *Zazavavindrano*, like the *Itrimobe*, is also from the Merina creation myth (Andrianjafitrimo, 2003). Haring describes them as maidens coming from the sea who marry mortal men, but disappear back into the sea when a taboo is broken, carrying all or some of the children from their union (2002: 183). The *Zazavavindrano* is also known as the *Vazimba* in Malagasy mythology, of which the most famous is the story of Ranoro, to whom the Antehiroka's ancestor, Andriambodilova, proposed marriage. She warned him of the *fady* (taboo) against using salt or even mentioning it, which of course he eventually broke, causing her to disappear back into the sea (Graeber, 2007: 222-223).

The two stories in the database that make reference to a water maiden are '*Renn Mer*' or 'The Queen of the Sea' (ATU 563 Table, Donkey, and Stick) and '*Kader*' (ATU 554 The Grateful Animals). '*Renn Mer*' revolves around the power of the water maiden to gift wishes to a mortal man. '*Kader*', on the other hand, actually involves the water maiden marrying a mortal man, twice. Once she marries a king who sent his servant, Kader, to fetch her from the sea, after hearing that she is the most beautiful woman in the universe. The king is bedazzled by her otherworldly beauty, but he cannot keep up with her immortality. Then she marries the hero, Kader, who has been gifted with the elixir of youth, thus himself becoming immortal.

There is another group of stories which are similar in pattern to the water maiden plot. These are three stories featuring otherworldly wives that disappear after a taboo is broken. They are '*Madanm Ki Ti Port Lasans*' (The Lady Who Brought Luck), '*Moulong*' (The Wife Made out of Wood Chips) and '*Fanmir Sousouri*' (The Wife Who Was a Bat). Though none of these women are actually water maidens, they are nevertheless otherworldly wives who disappear after their husbands have broken a personal taboo. This is precisely what happens in '*Fanmir Sousouri*', where the wife, who was a bat transformed into human shape, disappeared with all her

children when her husband broke the taboo of being unkind to her. In ‘The Lady Who Brought Luck’, a wooden effigy of his wife, made by a hunter, comes to life, but is transformed back into wood when the husband is unable to prevent himself from touching her before the assigned time. Mouloung is again a wooden effigy, more precisely, a wife made of bark, that comes to life when the husband sticks a hairpin in her head. Here we have the reverse of the Orange Princess story as the personage becomes lifeless after the pin is removed as punishment for cheating on her husband.

One might argue that there is not enough evidence to confirm that these stories are indeed connected to the Malagasy *Zazavavindrano*. Indeed, the story entitled ‘The Queen of the Sea’, is in fact almost an exact replica of an Indian tale entitled ‘Three Wishes’, except that the queen is replaced by a king (Kumar, 2020). As Seychelles has its own Indian connections (Nicholls, 2019: 58-59; 102-103; 186-187), the possibility that the story is of direct Indian heritage is not to be dismissed. In view of the comparatively high percentage of Malagasy slaves who were brought to Seychelles, and who contributed to the population mix (Allen, 2001: 105), neither should the possibility of the *Zazavavindrano* figure having been transposed in the Indian story be disregarded. At any rate, all of these stories have some elements of the *Zazavavindrano* characteristics, whether it be the beauty of the queen in ‘*Kader*’, or the wives who disappear because of a broken taboo (Haring, 2002: 183). Though such stories are not as widespread as the Loulou, Tizan, or Soungoula stories, they are nevertheless part of the Seychellois heritage of mythical creatures which have island-hopped into their folklore.

Conclusion

The Seychellois folktale repertoire is a very rich amalgamation of characters, patterns, and traditions that is representative of the islands’ role as a cultural crossroads. The mythical creatures and monsters that inhabit these folktales are at once, catalysts and products of creolization. If, for example, Soungoula is clearly an African heritage issuing from the tradition of animal tales, its reinterpretation in Seychelles has transformed it into a mythical creature that is nowhere near the description of a clever hare. Instead, it has become representative of the traumatic impact of slavery, the need for adaptation, and the power of resistance. To be more precise, in Seychellois stories, Soungoula is often stereotyped into the likeness of slave descendants, survives through his wit, and constantly makes a fool of authority. As such, Soungoula might be said to have been mythicized through the creolization process.

Loulou, on the other hand, has been rationalized into an ordinary wolf, in the process of linguistic adaptation. From a malevolent spirit, in the Malagasy language, it has become a symbol of the European ‘big bad wolf’, in the Seychellois narrative and imagination.

However, the mythical aspects of Loulou which come from its original culture, have been retained through the survival of original stories which have undergone very little transformation from the time of their transference. In the Seychellois context, Loulou is also a product of hybridization in the pre-colonial era in that it represents both the Bantu swallowing monster and the Malagasy malevolent spirit. Generally, this comes out in all the older, original stories, whereas in new Loulou stories, he is simply an animal character who interacts with other animals, and is portrayed as either a simple miscreant or a dupe (Choppy, 2022).

As for the vanishing women, only a few seem to have been transferred into the Seychellois folktale repertoire. They thus remain fairly obscure, nor do there seem to be any new stories created in that context. As a group, these stories about mythical creatures and monsters represent the Indian Ocean World context of this region's creolization process. They are the links in a network of islands and coastlines that connected through migration and trade. Finally, they settled and merged in these remote islands through colonialism and slavery. They are now part of the Seychellois cultural heritage in a truly melting pot perspective.

References

- Abel, A. (1981). *Contes des Seychelles*. Paris : Clé International.
- Allen, R.B. (2001). 'Licentious and Unbridled Proceedings: The Illegal Slave Trade to Mauritius and the Seychelles during the Early Nineteenth Century'. *The Journal of African History*, 42 (1), pp.91-116. Cambridge University Press. Stable URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3647217>
- Andrianjafitrimo, L. (2003). *La femme malgache en Imerina au début du XXIe siècle*. Paris: Editions Karthala.
- Arne, A., Thompson, S. and Uther, H.J. (2014). 'Multilingual Folktale Database'. Powered by TEITOK, Maarten Janssen. Online. Retrieved from: https://sites.ualberta.ca/~urban/Projects/English/Content/ATU_Tales.htm
- Baker P. (1993). 'Assessing the African Contribution to French-Based Creoles'. In Salikoko S. Mufwene (ed.), *Africanisms in Afro-American Language Varieties*, 123-155. Athens, Georgia: University of Georgia Press.
- Baker, P. and Corne, C. (1982). *Isle de France Creole: Affinities and Origins*. Ann Arbor: Karoma Publishers.
- Beaujard, P. (1991). *Mythe et société à Madagascar (Tanala de l'Ikongo): le chasseur d'oiseaux et la princesse du ciel*. Paris: L'Harmattan.
- Benedict, M. and Benedict, B. (1982). *Men, Women and Money in Seychelles*. Berkeley, CA: California University Press.
- Blench, R. (2014). 'Using Diverse Sources of Evidence for Reconstructing the Past History of Musical Exchanges in the Indian Ocean'. *The African Archaeological Review*, 31 (4), pp.675-703. Special Issue: Africa and the Indian Ocean.

- Callaway, H. (1868). *Nursery Tales Traditions and Histories of the Zulus, in their own words, with a translation into English*. Springvale, Natal: JA Blair in association with London: Trubner.
- Campbell, G. (1981). 'Madagascar and the Slave Trade, 1810-1895'. *The Journal of African History*, 22 (2), pp.203-227. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/181583>
- Chaudenson, R. and Ottino, P. (1977). 'Langues, cultures et sociétés de l'océan Indien. Asie du sud-est et monde insulindien.' 8 (3-4), pp.219-251, ASEMI.
- Chaudenson, R. (1992). *Des Iles, des hommes, des langues*. Paris: L'Harmattan.
- Chaudenson, R. (2001). *Creolization of Language and Culture*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Choppy, P. and Salomon, N. (2004). *Soungoula ek Bann Konper*, Au Cap, Seychelles: Creole Institute.
- Choppy, T.P. (2022). *Creativity, Creolization and Identity in Seychellois Creole Folktales*. PhD thesis, University of Malta.
- Dahle, L.R.P. (1877). *Specimens of Malagasy Folklore*. Antananarivo: A. Kingdon.
- Diallo, A., Rosalie, M., Essack, G. and Labiche, E. (1981). *Zistwar Sesel* (Folk Tales of Seychelles). Mahé: Oral Traditions Section, Culture Division.
- Diallo, A., Rosalie, M., Essack, G. and Labiche, E. (1983). *Contes, Devinettes et Jeux de Mots des Seychelles*. Paris : Editions Akpagnon.
- Dseagu, S. (2021). 'The Swallowing Monster in Southern African Folklore: Need for Morphological Investigation'. *Academia Letters*, Article 1963. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL1963>
- Franda, M. (1982). *The Seychelles: Unquiet Islands*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
- Geider, T. (2007). 'Alfu Lela Ulela: The Thousand and One Nights in Swahili-speaking East Africa'. In Marzolph, Ulrich (ed.), *The Arabian Nights in Transnational Perspective*, 183-200. Detroit, MI: Wayne State University Press.
- Golden, C. (2014). 'Spiritual Roots of the Land: Hierarchy and Relationships of the Religious Cosmologies of Humans and Their Environment in the Maroantsetra Region of Madagascar'. *Worldviews*, 18 (3), pp.255-268. Published by Brill. Stable URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43809588>
- Graeber, D. (2007). *Lost People: Magic and the Legacy of Slavery in Madagascar*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Haase, D. (2008). *The Greenwood Encyclopedia of Folktales and Fairy Tales: G-P. Volume 2*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.
- Haring, L. (2002). 'African Folktales and Creolization in the Indian Ocean Islands'. *Research in African Literatures*, Indiana University Press, (Autumn), 33 (3), pp.182-199. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.com/stable/3820689>
- Haring, L. (2003). 'Techniques of Creolization'. *The Journal of American Folklore*, 116 (459), pp.19-3. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4137940>
- Haring, L. (2005). 'Eastward to the Islands: The Other Diaspora'. *The Journal of American Folklore*, 118 (469), pp.290-307. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4137915>

- Haring, L. (2007). *Stars and Keys: Folktales and Creolization in the Indian Ocean*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Horton, M. and Middleton, T. (2010). *The Swahili: The Social Landscape of a Mercantile Community*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Jacottet, A. (1908). *The treasury of Ba-suto lore; being original Se-suto texts, with a literal English translation and notes*. Morija, Basutoland: Sesuto Book Depot in association with London: Kegan, Paul, Trench, Trubner & Co.
- Junod, H.A. (1897). *Les Chants et les Contes de Ba-Ronga de la Baie de Delagoa*. Lausanne, Switzerland: Georges Bridel.
- Kumar, K. (2020). 'Short Kid Stories.' [Online]. Retrieved from <https://www.shortkidstories.com/story/the-three-wishes/>
- Mazrui, A.M. (2016). *Cultural Politics of Translation: East Africa in a Global Context*. New York: Routledge.
- McPherson, K. (1984). 'Processes of Cultural Interchange in the Indian Ocean: An Historical Perspective'. *The Great Circle*, 6 (2), pp.78-92. Australian Association for Maritime History.
- Nicholls, P.A. (2019). *The Door to the Coast of Africa: Seychelles in the Mascarene Slave Trade, 1770–1830*. PhD Thesis, University of Kent. <https://kar.kent.ac.uk/67029>
- Ottino, P. (1974). 'L'Océan Indien comme domaine de recherche'. *L'Homme*, 14 (3-4), pp.143-151. Retrieved from https://www.persee.fr/doc/hom_0439-4216_1974_num_14_3_367487
- Ottino, P. (2013). 'Les aventures de Petit Jean : les aspects bantou et malgache'. *Études Océan Indien*, 49 (50), pp.33-41, (2nd ed.). INALCO. Retrieved from <http://journals.openedition.org/oceanindien/1832>
- Scarr, D. (2000). *Seychelles since 1770: History of a Slave and Post-Slavery Society*. London: Hurst and Company.
- Schottenhammer, A. (ed.). (2019). 'Early Global Interconnectivity across the Indian Ocean World: Volume II – Exchange of Ideas, Religions, and Technologies'. *Palgrave Series in Indian Ocean World Studies*. Retrieved from: <https://www.palgrave.com/gp/book/9783319978000>
- Sharp, L.A. (2001). 'Wayward Pastoral Ghosts and Regional Xenophobia in a Northern Madagascar Town'. *Journal of the International African Institute*, 71 (1), pp.38-81 <https://www.jstor.org/journal/afrijinteafriins>
- Sheriff, A. and Teelock, V. (2016). 'Slavery and the Slave Trade in the Indian Ocean'. In A. Sheriff, V. Teelock, S.O. Wahab and S. Peerthum, *Transition from Slavery in Zanzibar and Mauritius*, pp.25-43. Published by CODESRIA. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322055158_Slavery_and_the_Slave_Trade_in_the_Indian_Ocean
- Theal, G. M. (1886). *Kaffir Folk-Lore: A Selection from the Traditional Tales Current among the People Living on the Eastern Border of the Cape Colony with Copious Explanatory Notes*. London: S. Sonnenschein, Le Bas & Lowrey.
- Vernet, T. (2013). 'East Africa – Slave Migrations'. In Wiley Blackwell (ed.), *Encyclopedia of Global Human Migration, HAL – Human and Social Sciences*. Retrieved from <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-00699148>
- Werner, A. (1933). *Myths and legends of the Bantu with 32 illustrations*. London: George G.Harrap & Co. <https://www.sacred-texts.com>.

Dr. Penda Choppy is the Director of the Creole Language and Culture Research Institute at the University of Seychelles. She was the Director of the Creole Institute of Seychelles from 1999 to 2014 when she became its CEO. She moved to the University of Seychelles in 2016. Penda studied English at Leeds University as an undergraduate (1992-1995) and obtained a Master's Degree (research) from the University of Birmingham, UK, in 2018. She completed a doctoral research degree with the Islands and Small States Institute, University of Malta, in January 2023. Her main research interests are the oral and written Creole traditions of the Western Indian Ocean, in the postcolonial and small island contexts.

penda.choppy@unisey.ac.sc